

Atomic absorption spectrophotometric determination of tryptophan and cysteine^ψ

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Abstract : A novel method for determination of cysteine and tryptophan using atomic absorption spectrophotometry has been developed in which these substances are allowed to react with methanol solution of iodine there by iodide ions are released quantitatively and the released iodide ions are allowed to react with excess amount of silver nitrate for formation of equivalent amount of silver iodide precipitate. The excess of silver ions were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometry and from total amount of silver ions added, the concentration of liberated iodide ions was calculated. The equivalent amount of cysteine or tryptophan was then calculated.

Values obtained using this method were found to be comparable with the values obtained by conductometric titration.

Keywords : Cysteine, tryptophan, atomic absorption spectrophotometry.

Introduction

Proteins are vital for life. These are essential constituent of all living cells. They perform diverse biological function in the living systems. They are important for human and animal nutrition. The change in protein concentration or structure can be measured by using silver sulphide ion-selective electrode¹. A number of methods have been reported for the determination of proteins²⁻⁶. In enzymatic studies one is often faced with the problem that the characterization of a purified unknown protein requires an accurate determination of its concentration⁷. Spackman, Stein and Moore⁸ established cation-exchange chromatography method for amino acid analysis which is widely used⁹⁻¹⁶.

Cysteine is a naturally occurring sulfur containing amino acid. It strengthens the protective lining of the stomach and intestine, detoxify the body from harmful toxins and helps to protect the brain and liver from damage from alcohol, drugs etc. Tryptophan is an essential amino acid. It is a natural sedative and precursor for serotonin, melatonin. Determination of tryptophan is published in the AOAC official methods of analysis¹⁷. Sensitive determination of dissolved tryptophan in fresh water by alkaline hydrolysis and HPLC have been reported^{18,19}. Electrochemically driven derivatisation detection of

cysteine has been reported²⁰. In the present work an attempt has been made to determine cysteine and tryptophan by atomic absorption spectrophotometry. The results thus obtained were also verified by conductometry.

Results and discussion

The determination of cysteine and tryptophan is based on the reaction of cysteine or tryptophan with iodine-methanol solution which results in liberation of iodide ions which is then allowed to react with silver ion for the formation of precipitate of silver iodide. A known amount of silver ion is added to the solution and the excess of silver ion was determined by AAS method and then the amount of liberated iodide was calculated to find out the concentration of cysteine or tryptophan.

In another method, the reaction between liberated iodide ion and Ag⁺ ion added was followed by conductometric titration.

The effect of pH on the solubility of silver iodide is a vital test for the precipitation titration. Therefore, the conductivity of the solution was measured at different pH values. In case of both tryptophan and cysteine, it was observed (Fig. 2) that the conductivity decreases and comes to a minimum value at pH 3 and then rises. This indicates that the solubility of silver iodide is minimum at pH 3.

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For determining the amount of cysteine by AAS method, three sample solutions of cysteine were prepared. In this procedure 5 mL, 7 mL and 10 mL of 0.1 M cysteine solution was taken in three different beakers. After this 5 mL of 0.3 M iodine-methanol solution was added in 5 mL cysteine solution, 7 mL in 7 mL cysteine solution and 10 mL in 10 mL cysteine solution. These solutions were kept for 10 min at 35 °C and 1 mL of sulphuric acid was also added. To each beaker excess of 0.3 M silver nitrate solution was added. A yellow precipitate of AgI was formed in each beaker. The precipitate was filtered through a Whatman filter paper and then washed. To each filtrate 1 mL of nitric acid was added and the excess of silver ions were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometry.

The silver ions used in the formation of precipitate were calculated. This calculated value of silver nitrate is equivalent to the taken amount of cysteine in the sample. Thus cysteine was indirectly determined by AAS method. All the experimental work was done under the optimum pH condition.

Exactly the same procedure was followed for the determination of 0.01 M cysteine solution and tryptophan by AAS method. The results obtained for both the proteins are summarized in Table 1.

Conductometric titration²¹: In this procedure the filtrate of the sample solution was taken in a separate beaker and a conductometric electrode was inserted in this

Table 1. Determination of cysteine and tryptophan by atomic absorption spectrometry and conductometry

Sample	Amount taken (mg)	Recovery (%)	RSD (%)	F-test	Student t-test
Atomic absorption spectrometry					
Cysteine	121.2	96.3	1.77	1.12	1.51
	1212	97.0	1.87	0.53	1.69
Tryptophan	204.2	98.1	0.52	4.39	1.15
	2042	97.5	0.88	1.14	1.36
Conductometry					
Cysteine	121.2	97.5	1.87	1.12	1.94
	1212	97.6	1.35	0.53	1.95
Tryptophan	204.2	98.3	1.09	4.39	1.73
	2042	98.2	0.94	1.14	1.89

RSD – Relative standard deviation (three determinations).

F-test – Based on comparing standard deviation of proposed two method.

$n = 3$, Tabular t value for degree of freedom 2 is 4.303, and tabular F value for degree of freedom 2 is 19 and at 95% confidence level the values are obtained.

Fig. 1. Atomic absorption calibration curve for Ag⁺ ions.

solution. This solution was titrated with standard (0.1 M) KI solution. The volume of KI used in the titration corresponds to the amount of unused silver ions. The results obtained by this method are summarized in Table 1.

Thus we see that there is a good agreement in results obtained by both the techniques.

The conductometric titration method involves the direct determination of liberated iodide ion by cysteine or tryptophan whereas in atomic absorption method the excess of silver ion is determined and thus leading to an indirect determination of iodide ions. However, both the methods give the same result and therefore, either of these methods could be used for estimation of cysteine or tryptophan.

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on the conductivity of AgI precipitate.

Experimental

Reagents: A.R. grade of cysteine (Ridel De Halen), tryptophan (Loba Chemie), iodine (Sisco Research Laboratory), methanol (Qualigens), hydrochloric acid (Merck), sodium hydroxide (Thomas Baker), nitric acid (Merck) and silver nitrate (Thomas Baker) were used.

Instrument used : pH values were measured using Century (India) CP 901 digital pH meter. AAS measurements were carried out using GBC (Australia) Avanta Version 1.32. Conductometric measurements were carried out using Systronics (India) conductometer model 304.

Standard solution for AAS : Standard solution of silver nitrate was prepared by dissolving 1.5887 g of silver nitrate into a 1000 mL measuring flask : 50 mL of nitric acid was also added and the volume was made up to the mark with distilled water. Ag^{I} was measured by AAS in the absorption mode at 328.1 nm using air/acetylene flame. A slit width of 0.5 nm was used. The lamp current was 2.3 mA with a burner height of 11.4 cm and gas flow of 1.60 L/min.

Working solutions of lower concentrations were prepared by dilution from the stock standard solutions. From the 1000 mg/L Ag^{I} solution, solutions of 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0 and 5.0 mg/L of Ag^{I} were prepared. From these solutions straight line calibration graph was obtained (Fig. 1).

0.01 M hydrochloric acid and 0.01 M sodium hydroxide solutions were used for the adjustment of pH. A 0.1 M cysteine solution was prepared by dissolving the accurate weight of cysteine into distilled water and also 0.1 M tryptophan solution was prepared by dissolving it into distilled water. Solution of 0.3 M iodine methanol and silver nitrate were prepared by dissolving required amount of iodine into methanol and silver nitrate into distilled water. To this silver nitrate solution 10 mL of nitric acid solution was also added.

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